

Dynamo

Dynamic Spatio-Temporal Modulation
of Light by Phononic Architectures.

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D2.1 Selection and characterization of the most influential features and design parameters for the considered phononic structures

Date: 29 February 2024

D.2.1: Selection and characterization of the most influential features and design parameters for the considered phononic structures.

WP2. T.2.1: Sensitivity study of the cluster components and their assemblies

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Dynamo D.2.1: Selection and characterization of the most influential features and design parameters for the considered phononic structures.

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4. Introduction

4.1. Executive Summary

This document outlines the goal and scope of the work carried out in WP2 in relation to task T2.1. Following the scope of task T2.1, its main assumptions rely on analysing cluster components, here: pillars, as considered in WP1, and their spatial patterns. The key element of this task is to investigate and understand relations between the geometrical and material features of the samples and their dynamic properties, and to select those parameters that are of particular importance to the design.

In this document, we report on the theoretical background for the methods used, implementation activities carried out and the results obtained. The main purpose of this document is to report on deliverable D2.1, which is focused on analysing considered structures' dynamic responses and selecting the most influential parameters for the design:

D2.1: Selection and characterization of the most influential features and design parameters for the considered phononic structures. (M24)

The above-mentioned goal was achieved through the sensitivity analysis. For this purpose a systematic analysis approach was adopted, which consisted of the following steps:

- geometrical and numerical modelling of the structures, including their parametrization (both at the geometrical and numerical level),
- developing a framework for model generation, analysis and results collection,
- selecting and adapting methods for the sensitivity analysis,
- performing numerical analyses,
- postprocessing the results,
- analysis and selection of key parameters.

We focus on two types of numerical models of phononic structures: (a) containing one isolated cluster component (named as 1x1) in the unit cell, and (b) containing an array of 5-by-5 cluster components (named as 5x5). The latter model, constituting a supercell, allows for studying the influence of randomization of various geometrical parameters on the dynamic response.

4.2. Relation to Other Project Documents

This document does not refer to other project documents.

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4.3. Reference Documents

- [1] Campolongo F, Kleijnen J, Andres T (2000) Screening methods. In: Saltelli A, Chan K, Scott EM (eds) Sensitivity analysis. Wiley, Chichester, pp 65–80
- [2] Morris MD (1991) Factorial sampling plans for preliminary computational experiments. *Technometrics* 33:161–174
- [3] Helton J.C, Davis F.J (2003) Latin hypercube sampling and the propagation of uncertainty in analyses of complex systems, *Reliability Engineering & System Safety*, Volume 81, Issue 1,
- [4] Campolongo F, Cariboni J, Saltelli A (2007) An effective screening design for sensitivity analysis of large models. *Environ Modell Softw* 22:1509–1518

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5. Sensitivity analysis

As the sensitivity analysis is the key concept behind determining the influence and selecting key design parameters, we start by reviewing and commenting on the sensitivity analysis in the context of the relevant theory and assumptions.

5.1. Theory of the sensitivity analysis

Sensitivity analysis allows for quantification of the importance of various systems parameters to its response. As a consequence, the key design parameters can be selected and their influence on the response can be evaluated. The analysis can be performed once a model of the system is available, regardless of its type, in general. In the following analysis we will refer to numerical models of phononic structures.

The process of building a numerical model can be complex, especially when the relationships between inputs and outputs are uncertain/random. Sources of uncertainty can include both insufficient knowledge of the system and measurement errors, but also the influence of random phenomena. In such cases, the model can be treated as a “black box” in which the exact relationships between the inputs and outputs of the system are unknown. The process of sensitivity analysis (SA) is a study that identifies how the uncertainty in the model results can be attributed to different sources of uncertainty in the input data. It involves exploring a multidimensional space of input variables by cyclically solving a model for alternative initial parameters and determining sensitivity measures based on statistical quantities, thus determining which set of inputs has dominant effect on given outputs [1].

SA enables the identification and better understanding of relationships between input and output variables in the model without the need to examine all possible solution cases. This makes it possible not only to look for errors in the model but also to identify parameters that have negligible impact on the system. By identifying redundant parts of the model structure, it is possible to simplify the model, which translates directly into reduced design costs. SA is also often an integral part of the optimization process, in particular for the selection of the relevant optimization parameters (please note, that the developed framework will be further developed in the optimization tasks of the project).

The general SA procedure can be outlined as follows:

- determining the number of input variables in the assumed ranges of variability or probability distribution,
- determining the number and type of output parameters to be analysed,
- carrying out calculations of the model N times, determining the results for input variables changing within the full assumed range of variability,
- calculating sensitivity measures,

- determining mutual interactions between the inputs and their importance.

For the studies performed and reported in this document, we consider the one-factor-at-a-time (OAT or Morris) method. In this approach we attempt to evaluate the output parameters sensitivities to the inputs by screening the parameters' space in a statistical sense. Depending on the number and variability range of the inputs, the parameters' space can contain a large number of points to be investigated. To avoid the necessity of checking all possible combinations of the inputs, a number of statistically-driven samples (trajectories) is selected and evaluated to compute the sensitivity measures.

In particular, the OAT method involves solving the model for one changing input variable while keeping the remaining parameters unaffected. After completing the assumed number of cycles, the tested variable is restored to its unaffected value and the procedure is repeated in the same way for the next parameter. The main assumption of this approach is that any change observed in the model output will result from a change in a specific (one) input variable. The sensitivity of the model to changes in an input parameter can be determined using statistical measures. Figure 5.1.1 summarises the sensitivity analysis flowchart.

The SA method proposed in 1991 by Morris [2] was used in the current study, which is particularly well suited, for models with a large number of uncertain factors and/or when model calculations are expensive. Sensitivity analysis is performed for a given number of J model input variables examining their effects and interactions on output parameters. Each variable can take values in the assumed (predefined) range. Thus, the set of model input parameters under study forms a multidimensional space, including all possible combinations of available values for the parameters. By moving by a fixed jump value sequentially through all coordinates in the J -dimensional space, a single trajectory is created, which is a set of model inputs, based on which the model outputs are determined. Thanks to this information, it is possible to track changes in the output parameters of the model with a specific change in a given input variable. It involves calculating, for each input signal, a series of incremental coefficients, called elementary effects (EE), as

$$EE_{i,j} = \frac{f(x_1, \dots, x_i + \Delta, \dots, x_j) - f(x)}{\Delta}, \quad \Delta = \frac{1}{p-1} \quad (1)$$

where $f(x)$ is the model response for successive steps of the trajectory, J is the number of input variables, Δ is the fixed (normalised) discretization step the sensitivity grid and p is the number of levels for each variable in the J -dimensional space.

The number of evaluated elementary effects should be large enough to cover the J -dimensional space of input variables within the assumed ranges of variability. For this purpose, a set of trajectories with randomly selected starting points is created to effectively cover the entire parameter space, with each trajectory providing one EE for each model parameter. The process of generating the trajectories is carried out in a

normalised space (i.e. where the range of variation of each dimension is between 0 and 1 or, in general, is mapped to this normalised domain). The trajectories are then converted to the actual range of parameter variation. Figure 5.1.2.a shows 45 randomly selected starting points for the three input variables considered in the study of the 5x5 model. The distribution of starting points was generated using the Latin Hypercube Sampling method, which allowed for a uniform distribution of samples for each variable (Figure 5.1.3) [3].

Fig. 5.1.1 General scheme of the sensitivity analysis.

Fig.5.1.2 Trajectory calculation for SA in three-dimensional variable space: a) random distribution of starting points (Latin Hypercube sampling); b) trajectory generation for an example starting point; c) the set of all trajectories (example for the 5x5 model).

Fig. 5.1.3. Empirical distributions (sampled values of starting coordinates) for 3 factors, whose theoretical distributions are uniformly discrete with 9 levels using the Latin Hypercube sampling: a) ϕ , b) h , c) x_p, y_p .

Fig. 5.1.4. Empirical distributions (sampled values) for 3 factors: for all trajectories: a) ϕ , b) h , c) x_p, y_p .

The calculation of the model outputs is carried out for J factor values along n trajectories. Each trajectory consists of J steps, each of which changes only one factor

by a fixed step value Δ . During the generation of the trajectories, both the order of change of the parameters and the direction of change are randomly determined. Figure 5.1.2b shows the principle of generating an example trajectory. This results in $(J+1)*n$ sets of input variables. Figure 5.1.2c shows the set of all trajectories created from the starting points shown in Figure 5.1.2a. Figure 5.1.4 shows the sample distribution of each alternate input for all points used in the sensitivity analysis process. Figure 5.1.5 shows a flowchart for the trajectory database build process.

Fig. 5.1.5 . Flowchart of the build a trajectory database for SA

In the final step, two sensitivity measures are calculated to estimate the overall significance of the individual model parameters. The first parameter is the mean μ or modified mean μ^* [4], given by Eq. (2) which estimates the overall effect of the factor on the outcome. The second sensitivity measure is the standard deviation σ , given by Eq. (3), which estimates the ensemble of higher order effects of the factor, i.e. nonlinear and/or due to interactions with other factors

$$\mu_i^* = \frac{1}{N} \sum_{j=1}^N |EE_{ij}| \quad (2)$$

$$\sigma_i = \sqrt{\frac{1}{N-1} \sum_{j=1}^N (EE_{ij} - \mu_i^*)^2} \quad (3)$$

A large mean indicates a large factor effect. A large σ indicates that the effect depends strongly on the values of other factors, suggesting their non-linear interaction. Figure 5.1.6 shows a diagram of the interpretation of sensitivity measures for the results of sensitivity analysis as the coefficient of variance σ/μ^* . Figure 5.1.7 shows a flowchart for the determining the sensitivity measures.

Fig. 5.1.6. Interpretation of sensitivity measures for SA results.

Fig. 5.1.7 Scheme for determination of sensitivity measures.

5.2. Model geometry

In the current report we consider two types of samples, as mentioned before. These are samples consisting of square unit cells (in the x-y plane) and resembling a semi-infinite (half-)space with: (a) one cluster component (pillar) or (b) an array of 25 components in a cluster (5x5 arrangement of pillars). The geometry of both samples is shown in Figure 5.2.1.

The samples are parametrized by:

a - single unit cell edge length in the x-y plane,

s - substrate (finite) depth - z axis dimension,

ϕ - pillar diameter in x-y plane,

h - pillar height - z axis dimension,

x_p, y_p - pillar centre position in x-y plane with coordinate system centre in (0,0) of the component (i.e. the bottom left corner, see Figure 5.2.1).

Fig. 5.2.1. Geometry of a) single component, b) 5x5 cluster of components.

The unit cell is built out of a cuboid (the substrate layer) and a cylindrical pillar. The depth (i.e. the dimension in the z direction) of the substrate has to be sufficiently long in comparison to the unit cell side length, to avoid coupling of surface waves with the bottom face, hence promoting the Rayleigh-like waves to propagate as in a semi-infinite sample. Following a number of tests, we assumed the depth to be $20\times$ the unit cell edge length. The base pillar diameter and height are also taken with respect to the cluster edge length and are $0.7\times$ of this value. The dimensions are modified in a different way in the analysis of 1×1 and 5×5 clusters. In the case of 1×1 the diameter and height are modified in a deterministic way, in order to investigate the influence of cluster component features on the dynamics of the system, while in the 5×5 cluster of components diameter, height and position in x - y plane of every pillar are randomly modified assuming the normal distribution with the mean set to the nominal (base) value and a specified value of the standard deviation. Table 5.2.1 summarises the possible parameter ranges in the 1×1 case and for the 5×5 cluster (supercell). The randomised dimensions of the sample are verified against scenarios that may result in a non-physical setup or may lead to numerical issues (e.g. tangential contact of pillars). In case of a negative value of diameter or height in any of the pillars the random change is calculated again until positive values are generated. Values of x and y are the coordinates of the centre of a pillar. In the 1×1 model, the cross-section centre of a pillar has always the same x - y coordinates. In the 5×5 cluster, pillars are randomly shifted in the x - y plane (with the shifts along x and y being independent).

Table 5.2.1. Dimensions of a single component 1x1 cluster dimensions range and 5x5 cluster standard deviation range. The standard deviations applied in the randomization process of 5x5 sample are given later.

Component dimension symbol	Basic dimension of the component [μm]	1x1 tested range [μm]	5x5 mean [μm]
a	1.5	constant	-
s	$20a = 30$	constant	-
ϕ	$0.7a = 1.05$	0.525 : 1.5	$2(0.3 : 0.4)a$
h	$0.7a = 1.05$	0.5 : 2.6	$\phi \pm \phi/2$
x_p	$0.5a = 0.75$	constant	nominal*
y_p	$0.5a = 0.75$	constant	nominal*

* nominal values correspond to the central positions of the pillars.

The Bloch periodic boundary conditions were applied to the vertical faces of the model (i.e. assuming the periodicity in the x-y plane). The bottom surface of the substrate was fixed. Initially, an alternative approach with a Perfectly Matched Layer (PML) below the homogeneous substrate layer was implemented and tested. It was found, however, that this choice resulted in a number of numerical issues, e.g. complex eigenvalues, multiple artificial modes etc. (including multiple modes localised close to the PML layer). With the assumed substrate layer depth, selection of the fixed boundary condition allows one to find the wave modes of interest - modes with most energy localised at the surface - and compare them more easily. Figure 5.2.2 shows the 5x5 cluster with boundary conditions – the 1x1 case is analogous.

Figure 5.2.2. Two 5x5 cluster unit cells from an infinite system. Bloch boundary conditions are symbolised by red and blue arrows and corresponding phase shifts are shown. Fixed boundary condition is applied to the bottom faces. (Two unit cells are depicted for illustration purposes; one unit cell was analysed in FEM.)

The Bloch boundary condition of the form

$$u_{n+1}(x, k) = e^{ika} u_n(x, k).$$

was applied. The phase factor e^{ika} is based on unit cell size which is a for 1x1 and $5a$ for a 5x5 cluster in both x and y direction. The wavevector is given by $k = (k_x, k_y)$. The Brillouin zone for the 1x1 and the 5x5 cluster is shown in Fig. 5.2.3. In current analysis we use only a single wavevector located at the edge of the Brillouin zone $(k_x, 0)$. Choosing wavenumber at the edge of the Brillouin zone allows us to observe bandgaps and separate modes of interest in frequency domain.

Figure 5.2.3. Brillouin zones of a) unit cell with single component, b) unit cell with cluster of 5x5 components. Red points mark wavevectors selected for current analysis.

5.3. Numerical framework for sensitivity analysis of disordered crystals

We perform analyses using two main software tools: COMSOL Multiphysics and MATLAB and employ libraries that allow their coupling. This approach was selected to allow automatic model generation, performing simulations and postprocessing, from the MATLAB level. This combination of software tools allows for automatic analysis of hundreds of models required for the sensitivity analysis. The developed software framework will be used also in subsequent optimization studies.

Numerical analyses are performed with the Structural Mechanics module of COMSOL. Particular geometrical features of the models were outlined in the previous section. Material properties applied to the model were taken from the program database as polycrystalline silicon. For discretization we selected the second order tetrahedral serendipity elements to minimise the over-stiffening effects. Before selecting particular mesh properties (minimal and maximal element sizes and the transition rate) a convergence analysis was performed (described later in this section). The analysis consisted of an eigenvalue problem solution for a selected number of modes. It is worth noting that the parameters of the eigenproblem solution (e.g. number and range of eigenvalues) can be adjusted during model preparation and, consequently, modified between two consecutive models (e.g. adjusted based on the previous results obtained for a trajectory point).

The mesh convergence analysis requires multiple simulations with variable parameters, with the goal of obtaining accurate results with possibly low number of elements. For the mesh convergence we used basic component dimensions from the previous section and 1x1 cluster.

The convergence study included the following parameters:

- maximum element size,
- minimum element size,
- maximum element growth rate,
- curvature factor,
- resolution of narrow regions.

We started with the last three parameters with fixed values 1.25, 0.5 and 0.6 respectively and modified the maximum and minimum size of elements. Important model parameters found for the convergence analysis are summarised in Table 5.3.1. We distinguish three models: the medium mesh size model, the reference model with the finest mesh and the chosen model. We first find the result for the intermediate model. We chose the next model by decreasing the element size by a factor of 2. We calculate relative error for every eigenfrequency

$$e = \text{abs}(f_r - f)/f_r,$$

where f_r is frequency of an eigenmode in the reference model and f is frequency in the model being compared. If the maximum relative errors between these two models are less than 1%, we select the finer model to be the reference model. Otherwise, we repeat the mentioned procedure again but starting with a different, more precise intermediate model. When the reference model is found, we increase the element size to find the model which gives the maximum relative error below 3 % with respect to the reference model. The results of relative errors are presented in Fig. 5.3.1.

Table 5.3.1. Mesh parameters for models used in the 1st step of the convergence analysis - changing maximum and minimum element size.

Parameter	Reference model	Medium model	Chosen model
Max. element size	2e-4	4e-4	8e-4
Min. element size	2e-5	4e-5	8e-5
Number of elements	139458	17952	2192

Figure 5.3.1. Relative error for 3 models with maximum and minimum element size summarised in Table 5.3.1. Orange line shows relative errors of medium size model and blue line shows relative errors of the model chosen in the first step of the convergence analysis.

In the next step we increased the maximum element growth rate and decreased the number of elements not exceeding the limit of 3 % of the relative error. The parameters found by employing the above-mentioned procedure, were used in the sensitivity analysis. Parameters used in this step are summarised in Table 5.3.2 and the relative errors with changed elements growth rate are shown in Fig. 5.3.2.

Table 5.3.2. Mesh parameters for models used in the 2nd step of the convergence analysis - changing maximum element growth rate.

Parameter	Reference model	Chosen in 1st step	Final model
Maximum element growth rate	1.25	1.25	1.5
Number of elements	139458	2192	2056

Figure 5.3.2. Relative error for model chosen in the first step of the convergence analysis (orange dots) and model with final mesh parameters (blue lines).

The sensitivity analysis was performed with the developed MATLAB library of functions allowing for model generation, modification, simulation and result postprocessing. The functions, developed within task T2.1, are listed below along with detailed description. The functions allow for performing the sensitivity analysis of a cluster with a single component (1x1) and of a cluster of 5x5 components. Figure 5.3.3 presents a scheme of communication between MATLAB and COMSOL. It is the MATLAB layer that starts COMSOL internal procedures. Additionally there are only three MATLAB scripts that communicate with COMSOL directly.

Figure. 5.3.3. MATLAB - COMSOL communication scheme. Three MATLAB scripts directly call COMSOL procedures.

The scripts in Fig. 5.3.3 calculate the results for only a single wavenumber (singleK). We also limit the number of computed eigenvalues to 50. We found that in this range we can find the set of eigenvalues with properties we seek i.e. there are multiple surface localised modes in the selected range of frequencies.

The sensitivity analysis of 1x1 cluster uses multiple MATLAB scripts and functions. The most important elements of the solution are summarised in Fig. 5.3.4. There are multiple data files created during the analysis. Here are descriptions of the symbols used in Fig. 5.3.4.

SAD - Sensitivity Analysis Data - contains the parameters that varied during the analysis including pillars' radius and height ranges.

MD - Model Data - each time the function build_rand_model_singleK is used to create a model it saves model parameters to a new file.

ED - Extracted Data - this file contains data extracted from the COMSOL model. It contains natural frequencies and data of modes shapes gathered from the requested number of points. Selection of the points is described later in this paragraph.

M1 - Model 1 - COMSOL model file which contains created model but without calculated eigenvalues and eigenvectors.

M2 - Model 2 - COMSOL model file which contains created model and calculated eigenpairs.

Figure 5.3.4. Most important script and function used in the sensitivity analysis of the 1x1 cluster of components. SAD, MD, ED, M1 and M2 are files containing data and COMSOL models.

The scheme for analysis of the unit cells containing 5x5 clusters of components is shown in Fig. 5.3.5. It is similar but has some important differences. First, the trajectories for the Morris method are generated in a separate script before running the main loop with models building and analysis. The function `build_rand_model_singleK` receives base model parameters and randomization parameters (standard deviations) and calls `build_comsol_model_singleK` function with randomised model parameters. Below is the description of the file symbols.

SAD - Sensitivity Analysis Data - contains trajectories in randomisation parameters space.

MD - Model Data - each time the function `build_rand_model_singleK` is used to create a model it saves model parameters to a new file. Both base model data and randomised model data are saved.

ED - Extracted Data - the same as in 1x1x case. This file contains data extracted from the COMSOL model. It contains natural frequencies and data of modes shapes gathered from the requested number of points. Selection of the points is described later.

M1 - Model 1 - the same as in 1x1x case. COMSOL model file which contains created model but without calculated eigenvalues and eigenvectors.

M2 - Model 2 - the same as in 1x1x case. COMSOL model file which contains created model and calculated eigenpairs.

Figure. 5.3.5. Most important script and function used in the sensitivity analysis of the 5x5 cluster of components. SAD, MD, ED, M1 and M2 are files containing data and COMSOL models.

We extract data from COMSOL models to MATLAB for the part of the analysis not implemented in COMSOL software. Data we extract include natural frequencies (eigenvalues) and vibration profiles (eigenvectors) at specified points arranged in layers. We use four layers in the current analysis. Figure 5.3.6 shows an example mode shape and data points arrangement.

Figure. 5.3.6. Data extraction points, a) example mode shape (scaled) close to the surface, b) scheme of the points arranged in layers. Each of 4 layers contains 5 points. The radius at which 4 points are located is 95% of the base radius value. The 5th point is located at the centre of the cross section. The last layer is located at 95% base height of the pillar. Species between layers are equal.

The description of all the MATLAB functions and scripts used in the analysis is given next. Some of them are not included in figures to make the schemes more readable.

work_loop_1x1_RH - script. It is used to run the main loop of the 1x1 cluster analysis. It uses `calculateModel_nxn` to prepare results from models with assumed range of pillar radius and height. It saves the sensitivity data (i.e. parameters ranges) to a new file.

Morris_TR - script. It is used to generate trajectories in randomisation parameters space for 5x5 clusters analysis. It saves generated trajectories to a new file.

work_loop_5x5_RHXY_LHC - script. It is used to run the main loop of the 5x5 cluster analysis. It uses `calculateModel_nxn` to prepare results from models with assumed base and randomisation parameters - radius, height and position of each of the pillars.

calculateModel_nxn - function. It works differently in 1x1 and 5x5 analysis.

In 1x1 analysis it takes 3 input variables: model data, id for radius in analysed range and id for height in analysed range.

In 5x5 analysis it takes 5 input variables: number of components in each direction - here always 5, randomisation parameters - standard deviations, scaling factor for randomisation parameters, trajectory number and number of samples within the trajectory.

In both analyses the function prepares data required to build the COMOSL model, and creates data structures with eigensolution settings. Then it calls functions `build_rand_model_singleK`, `run_comsol_model_singleK` and `extractDataSingleK_Layers` to build the COMSOL model, calculate eigenpairs and extract data for further analysis. Function return three file names for COMSOL model, COMSOL model with calculated solution and for mat-file with extracted data.

`build_rand_model_singleK` - function. It takes 4 input variables: structure with pillars base data, randomisation parameters, eigensolution requirements and a string to add to the end of the COMSOL model file name.

In 5x5 analysis only it applies randomisation. Base value of each parameter is taken as a mean value and standard deviations are provided in the second input variable. It also prepares the part of the future file name which depends on the randomisation - randomised parameters are present in a file name.

It prepares all the data to call `build_comsol_model_singleK` which communicates with COMSOL to build the model. Function returns a file name of the built COMSOL model.

It saves both base and randomised data to a new file.

`build_comsol_model_singleK` - function. It takes 9 input variables: COMSOL model file name, structure with data of each (position, radius, height), normalised wavenumber, number of modes to find, approximate number of modes (eigensolution in range of frequency), boolean that tells to find solution in the frequency range, structure with frequency range data, boolean that tells to find solution close to a given frequency, and frequency which solver should search for solution around.

It establishes communication with COMSOL and creates a model with given parameters and solution requirements. It saves the COMSOL model to a new file.

`run_comsol_model_singleK` - function. It takes a single input variable: COMSOL model file name. It finds the eigenpairs and creates a new COMSOL model file. It returns a file name of the new model.

`extractDataSingleK_Layers` - function. It takes four input variables: file name of the file created by `build_rand_model_singleK` function, file name for a new m-file, number of additional data layers (there are at least two layers - in this analysis we use four layers), frequency range in which the data is extracted.

It opens the COMSOL model file with results and extracts natural frequencies and vibration shapes in points presented in Fig. 5.3.6. It saves extracted data to a new file.

`positiveRandomizedVector` - function. It takes two input variables: mean value and standard deviation. It is used inside the `build_rand_model_singleK` function to

randomise for which we allow only positive values. It returns a randomised positive value.

5.4. Sensitivity analysis of cluster components

In the first stage of the study, a sensitivity analysis was conducted for the single component numerical model (Fig. 5.2.1.a), exploring the effect of changing the diameter of the pillar ϕ and its height h on the eigenfrequencies. Due to the numerical model's non-complexity and consequently low computational cost, the study applied the brute-force method, which involves determining the output parameters for all possible combinations of input variables from an assumed range of changes.

For this purpose, the 2-dimensional space of ϕ and h variables were divided into 25 intervals in each direction. Thus, 26 fixed values of the pillar diameter and corresponding 26 fixed values of the pillar height from the given range were obtained, resulting in 676 pairs of values forming the input parameter base of the numerical model. The ranges of changes in parameters ϕ and h are shown in Table 5.2.1. The frequency change and frequency difference of neighbouring vibration modes included in the selected frequency range were taken as the observed result of the model.

5.5. Sensitivity analysis of clusters

The sensitivity analysis was carried out for a cluster of 5x5 pillars, which included 3 geometric parameters, i.e. pillar position, diameter and height, creating a 3-dimensional space of model input variables. Each dimension of the variable space was divided into 10 equal compartments, forming a grid of 1331 nodal points, which were the basis for the process of creating the trajectory base. This process is described in Section 4.1 and illustrated by the diagram of Fig. 5.1.5. Changes in the geometry of the pillars are independent and the value of each parameter is random and determined under the following assumptions of the randomisation process

- normal distribution,
- the mean equal to the base parameter value*,
- controlling the randomization process by changing the scaling factor affecting the covariances:

$$C = sc_1 * D/2 \text{ (x,y coord, diameter)}$$

$$C = sc_2 * H \text{ (height)}$$

*technically, the base value of a parameter is implemented in the nominal model and a parameter shift is computed assuming the zero-mean distribution. Finally, the randomised value is added to the base value of a parameter.

The covariance matrix contains the standard deviations for all combinations of the input parameters, here these are the x and y coordinates shifts. In the current study, we assume that the covariance matrix is diagonal, hence we do not assume any inter-relations between the shifts along the x and y axes (and other parameters). As a consequence, the covariance matrix is diagonal. Furthermore, for the same assumptions for the x and y axes (i.e. no one of the axes is privileged), the covariance matrix takes the form of the diagonal matrix.

$$\Sigma = \begin{bmatrix} \sigma_1^2 & \sigma_{12}^2 & \sigma_{13}^2 & \sigma_{14}^2 \\ \sigma_{21}^2 & \sigma_2^2 & \sigma_{23}^2 & \sigma_{24}^2 \\ \sigma_{31}^2 & \sigma_{32}^2 & \sigma_3^2 & \sigma_{34}^2 \\ \sigma_{41}^2 & \sigma_{42}^2 & \sigma_{43}^2 & \sigma_4^2 \end{bmatrix} \quad \Sigma = \begin{bmatrix} sc_1 * 1 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & sc_2 * 1 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & sc_1 * 1 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & sc_1 * 1 \end{bmatrix}$$

The sc factor can range between 0 (indicating no randomisation) and an experimentally determined maximum value for which the full range of assumed parameter variability is available. The frequency change and frequency difference of adjacent vibration modes were taken as the observed output of the model. Elementary effects are calculated based on changes in the frequencies of specific modes and change in the frequency differences of pairs of neighbouring modes.

6. Results of the sensitivity analysis

6.1. Technical considerations

Based on the observations during the stage of performing simulations, collecting data and processing the results, it is possible to identify the main problems that may also be significant at further stages of the research. These problems are:

- high computational cost for the 5x5 model forces to explore the possibility of simplifying the numerical model (e.g., by reducing the density of the finite element mesh or limiting the number of calculated output parameter values), reverting to analytical models,
- the need for verification and filtering of results due to the appearance of outliers (models whose results differ significantly from models with similar input parameters),
- the need for accurate identification of characters due to the appearance of characters with almost equal frequencies.

6.2. Sensitivity analysis of cluster components

Figure 6.2.1 shows a compilation of the results of numerical calculations performed for single component models. Each surface represents the frequency distribution for a particular mode over the full range of analysed cases of input variables. Blank cells correspond to cases where the results were extreme outliers compared to their neighbours (these include numerical issues with COMSOL models).

Fig. 6.2.1. Distribution of natural frequencies in the full space of input variables for the frequency range studied (single component).

Figures 6.2.2 a - h show frequency distributions for separate modes in the full range of input variable analysed cases. To better illustrate the effect of changes in individual variables on the frequencies of a given mode, the graphs were scaled individually.

a

b

c

d

e

f

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Fig. 6.2.2. Distribution of natural frequencies in the full space of input variables for the individual modes in the considered frequency range.

It is worth noting that for modes no. 1, 2, 5 and 7, the sensitivity to a change in the parameters ϕ and h is small with an equal effect of both parameters on the frequency. For other frequencies considered, it is the h parameter that has the greatest effect on the change in frequency. Intuitively, the largest decrease in frequency values occurred for the largest value of bar height and base bar diameter.

Fig. 6.2.3. Sensitivity measures for eigenfrequency.

Fig. 6.2.4. Sensitivity measures for eigenfrequency difference.

Figure 6.2.3 shows the coefficients of variance determined for the single component model. It includes all 8 modes, the distribution of which is presented in Fig. 6.2.1. Each marker denotes the coefficient of variance for one mode, taking into account the sensitivity to change in diameter (black marker) and height (red marker), respectively. Interpretation of the distribution of variance coefficients for both input variables allows the following conclusions:

- all coefficients of variance are near or above the line $\sigma/\mu^* = 1$ which, according to scheme 4.1.6, means a non-linear or/and non-monotonic dependence of the value of eigenfrequency on the variables,
- a change in the height of the bar has a far greater effect and interaction on the calculated model output than a change in diameter,
- noticeable greater sensitivity of specific characters to changes in geometric parameters of the post (characters number 3,4, 6 and 8).

These conclusions are confirmed by the analysis of coefficients of variance determined for frequency differences of adjacent characters, which are presented in Figure 6.2.4.

6.3. Sensitivity analysis of clusters

Figures 6.3.1 and 6.3.2 show, respectively, the coefficients of variance of frequencies and frequency differences calculated for the 5x5 cluster model with randomization. Each marker denotes the coefficient of variance for one mode, taking into account the

sensitivity to a change in input parameters (ϕ - black marker, h - red marker, x,y - blue marker)

Fig. 6.3.1 . Sensitivity measures for eigenfrequency

Fig. 6.3.2 . Sensitivity measures for eigenfrequency differences

The distribution of variance coefficients for all input variables allows for drawing the following conclusions:

- as in the case of a single component, all coefficients of variance are near or above the line $\sigma/\mu^* = 1$ (non-linear or/and non-monotonic relation of the values of natural frequency to the variables),
- changing the height of the pillars has a greater influence effect and interaction on the calculated model output than changing the diameter and changing the position of the pillars,
- the eigenfrequencies with higher values (modes number 13 and 14, which are closest to the upper limit of the considered frequency range) are more sensitive to changes in pillars height than the other modes,
- with regard to 13 and 14 eigenfrequencies, the influence of input variables on the other modes is much smaller.

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7. Conclusion

In the study referred to in the following report, two phononic structures were analysed for sensitivity to changes in geometric parameters: a single component and a cluster of 5x5 pillars. The diameter, height and position of the pillar were selected as the parameters under change. An additional assumption in the sensitivity analysis of the 25-pillars layout was the stochastic method of determining the values of changes in each parameter, individually for every pillar. Sensitivity analysis was carried out based on changes in eigenfrequencies within a defined frequency range and changes in frequency differences for neighbouring modes. Based on the results obtained, it can be concluded that:

- the biggest impact on the observed frequency parameters is the change in the height of the pillar,
- the effect of changing the geometry of the bar is primarily visible for higher frequencies,
- the interaction of the geometric parameters of the pillar is strongly nonlinear and/or non-monotonic,
- carrying out the study with the consideration of randomization of input variables (separately for each pillar) allowed to observe the impact of possible manufacturing errors that may arise at the stage of production of actual samples. The results obtained suggest that in a small range of changes, the impact of unintentional geometry errors will have a negligible effect on the properties of the structure.

